

Pretreatment of radioactive concentrate from lead-bismuth cooled fast reactors: flocculant screening and process optimization

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Academic editor: Peng Luo ♦ Received 30 September 2025 ♦ Accepted 3 March 2026 ♦ Published 25 March 2026

Citation: Peng S, Wang D, Li S, Li J, Xie H (2026) Pretreatment of radioactive concentrate from lead-bismuth cooled fast reactors: flocculant screening and process optimization. Nuclear Energy and Technology 12(1): 29-39. <https://doi.org/10.3897/nucet.12.173459>

Abstract

The processing of radioactive concentrates generated during the operation of lead bismuth fast reactors is extremely difficult, with complex components including heavy metals such as Pb and Bi, radioactive nuclides such as Cs, Sr, and Co, alpha emitters such as ²¹⁰Po, as well as organic matter and suspended particles. This study focuses on the pretreatment challenges of this radioactive liquid waste, systematically screening 13 types of mature commercial flocculants and evaluating their efficiency in the flocculative removal of key heavy metals and simulated radionuclides from the concentrate. The experimental results showed that the flocculant #9 had a removal efficiency of over 99% for Pb, Bi, and Co within 20 minutes, and a removal efficiency of 96% for the ²¹⁰Po analog element Te. The effluent pH was close to neutral, which was superior to other reagents. Through optimization via single-factor experiments and Response Surface Methodology, the optimal process parameters for flocculant #9 were determined as follows: pH 7.8, dosage of 1.17 g/L, and flocculation time of 15.9 minutes. This study provides an efficient and low-cost pretreatment process for radioactive concentrate from lead-bismuth reactors, which can significantly reduce the subsequent deep purification load of ²¹⁰Po and offers technical support for the optimization of nuclear waste liquid treatment processes.

Keywords

fission products, flocculation sedimentation, heavy metals, process optimization, response surface methodology (RSM), lead-bismuth reactor

Introduction

Lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs), as Generation IV reactor systems, have attracted significant attention due to their excellent neutronics characteristics, inherent safety, and thermo-hydraulic performance (Alemberti et al.

2011, 2014; Locatelli et al. 2013). Among them, liquid lead-bismuth alloy is used as the main coolant in the primary circuit to transfer the heat of the reactor. During the preparation of the lead-bismuth alloy, elements ¹⁰⁹Ag are contained, which are transformed into ¹¹⁰Ag under neutron irradiation. At the same time, the ¹³⁷Cs and ⁹⁰Sr produced

by the fission of the reactor core will gradually thematically diffuse from the coating material into the coolant (Khaled et al. 2021). The ^{55}Mn and ^{59}Co in the primary circuit structural material will be transformed into radioactive ^{54}Mn and ^{60}Co under neutron irradiation and enter the coolant under the corrosion of the lead-bismuth alloy (Zhang et al. 2019). Under strong neutron irradiation conditions, ^{209}Bi in lead-bismuth alloys will undergo fission to produce ^{210}Po (Nataliya et al. 2021). According to the engineering classification and discharge basis IAEA GS-G-1, the contaminated solutions brought by these radioactive elements are usually classified as LLW and ILW. This complexity poses extreme treatment challenges, and the exceptionally stringent discharge limit for ^{210}Po presents a severe challenge for its purification process. To achieve effective removal of ultralow concentrations of ^{210}Po from the concentrate and meet stringent discharge limits, pretreatment for high concentrations of interfering heavy metal ions is essential. Current treatment methods for heavy metal waste liquids include electrochemical treatment (Peng et al. 2020; Lun et al. 2023), ion exchange (Bashir et al. 2019), membrane filtration (Almasian et al. 2018), adsorption (Gu et al. 2019; Fei et al. 2021), electrodialysis (Jin et al. 2021), and flocculation precipitation (Moi et al. 2009). Among them, the flocculation sedimentation method has the advantages of high removal efficiency for complex heavy metal systems, simple operation, and low cost (Eleonora et al. 2015; Chen et al. 2018; Dai et al. 2020). Although the flocculation sedimentation method inevitably produces secondary radioactive sludge, it significantly reduces the volume of primary radioactive waste, thereby lowering treatment costs. Furthermore, radioactive sludge is expected to be reused as a radiation source to participate in water electrolysis for hydrogen production, improve hydrogen production efficiency, and achieve secondary utilization of waste (Alyazouri et al. 2025). The considerable application potential of the flocculation sedimentation method in the pretreatment of radioactive waste liquid.

Given that engineering applications emphasize process maturity and supply stability, this paper focuses on the systematic screening and optimization of “commercially mature flocculants”. Flocculants are generally categorized into organic and inorganic types. Common organic flocculants, such as polyacrylamide, polydimethylallylammonium chloride, and polyethyleneimine, primarily facilitate particle aggregation and sedimentation through charge neutralization and polymer bridging mechanisms (Peng et al. 2017). For example, Ding (Ding et al. 2023) reported that a polyacrylamide-glutathione composite flocculant achieved high removal efficiency (>95%) for Cr(VI) in water. Inorganic flocculants (e.g. ferric chloride (FeCl_3), polyaluminum chloride, aluminum sulfate ($\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$)) primarily facilitate flocculation through mechanisms such as double-layer compression, charge neutralization, as well as enmeshment and sweep coagulation (Eleonora et al. 2015). Mokhtar (Mokhtar et al. 2024) confirms that FeCl_3 has a removal efficiency of over 90%

for heavy metals such as Cd, Pb, Zn in domestic wastewater. In addition, researchers have also developed a variety of modified flocculants, such as the chitosan-based flocculant (cmcts-g-p (am-ca)) prepared by Sun (Sun et al. 2020) and the “carmine” pectin flocculant reported by Diana (Ibarra-Rodríguez et al. 2017) and others, which show excellent removal performance for heavy metal ions in complex matrices. However, the synthesis costs of these customized flocculants are typically high, and their long-term stability in practical radioactive wastewater treatment applications, as well as the volume of secondary waste generated, still require further evaluation. In contrast, mature commercial flocculants offer advantages for engineering applications, such as controllable costs, stable supply, and predictable performance.

Given the highly complex composition of lead-bismuth reactor concentrate and the practical demands of engineering applications, this study employs flocculation precipitation as a key pretreatment process to significantly reduce radionuclide load. Simultaneously, it diverges from the development of new materials, focusing instead on the systematic screening and optimization of commercially available mature flocculants. The specific research objectives are: (1) To screen commercial flocculants suitable for the pretreatment of lead-bismuth reactor concentrate; (2) To investigate the removal efficiency and mechanisms of selected flocculants for target heavy metal elements under varying pH, dosage, and time conditions; (3) To optimize the operational parameters of the preferred flocculant using an RSM model, investigating the optimum flocculant dose, pH, and flocculation time, thereby providing data support for its scaled-up engineering application.

Experimental materials and methods

Concentrate source term and chemical reagents

The simulated waste liquid components and concentrations are shown in Table 1, and are set based on the actual lead bismuth reactor concentrated liquid source data, provide referece(s) for liquid waste from lead bismuth reactor used as a basis for composition (Xing et al. 2022; Chen et al. 2025). For radiation safety considerations, Te (VI) (existing in the form of TeO_4^{2-}) was used in this study to simulate the behavior of Po (Zhou et al. 2017). This alternative solution is representative in the two main removal mechanisms of silver-sulfide precipitation/flocculation and sulfur-containing ligand complexation. However, it should be pointed out that Te and Po have differences in the chemical properties of the aqueous phase, such as valence state, hydrolyzability and colloidal behavior, etc. (Amaya et al. 2009; Rahul Ram et al. 2019; Xujie Chen et al. 2022). Therefore, the results of this study should not be directly extrapolated to the process dominated by Po(IV) hydrolysis/hydroxide precipitation. In summary, the optimal process parameters obtained for Te in this

Table 1. Chemical composition and concentration of simulated radioactive concentrate

Nuclear substances/heavy metals	Ionic form	Chemical composition / Analytical grade	Concentration (mg/L)
Cs	Cs ⁺	CsNO ₃	5
Sr	Sr ²⁺	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	5
Co	Co ²⁺	Co(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	10
Pb	Pb ²⁺	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	600
Bi	Bi ³⁺	Bi(NO ₃) ₃ ·5H ₂ O	750
Po(Simulate with Te)	TeO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ TeO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	5
Ag	Ag ⁺	Ag(NO ₃)	10
COD	/	CH ₃ COONa	5500
Salts	Na ⁺	NaNO ₃	2600

work are mainly applicable to the unit process dominated by silver-sulfide precipitation and sulfur-containing ligand complexation, while they only have qualitative reference value for the Po (IV) hydroxide precipitation process.

Other radionuclides were substituted with their non-radioactive counterparts. To closely simulate actual operational conditions, no additional solubilization treatments were applied to certain low-solubility components listed in Table 1. All analytical grade chemical reagents were purchased from Shanghai Aladdin Biochemical Technology Co., Ltd. The simulated waste liquid was prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of analytical grade reagents in laboratory-produced deionized water, followed by stirring at 500 rpm for 1 hour at room temperature.

The flocculants evaluated in this study were sourced as follows: #1 Cationic PAM C3 (Shouxin Environmental Protection Materials Technology Co., Ltd., abbreviated as S.H.). #2 Anionic PAM A100 (S.H.). #3 Zirconium Phosphate-Modified Anionic PAM (S.H.). #4 Heavy Metal Capturing Agent (Fuer Cheng Environmental Protection Technology Co., Ltd., abbreviated as F.E.). #5 Cobalt Removal Agent (F.E.). #6 Fly Ash Chelating Agent (F.E.). #7 Anionic PAM H02123 (S.H.). #8 MCP-4 Heavy Metal Capturing Agent (Nasen Environmental Protection Co., Ltd., abbreviated as N.S.). #9 PQ-500 Chelating Agent (N.S.). #10 Cationic PAM H01152 (S.H.). #11 Anionic PAM H01123 (S.H.). #12 Cationic PAM H01132 (S.H.). #13 Sodium Sulfide Chelating Agent (Laboratory-synthesized).

Experimental instruments

The experimental instruments include: pH meter (Model: PHS-3C, Shanghai Yidian Scientific Instrument Co., Ltd.), Electronic Balance (Shanghai Jinghai Precision Instrument Co., Ltd.), ICP-OES (ICPE-9800, Shimadzu), ICP-MS (NexION 350X, PerkinElmer), Laboratory-Grade Pure Water System (Nanjing Yipuda Technology Development Co., Ltd.), 6-chamber magnetic stirrer (HJ-6A, Jiangsu Jinyi Technology Co, Ltd.)

Experimental conditions design

All flocculation experiments were conducted in 500 ml beakers at 25 ± 2 °C, and the stirring process was controlled by a six-bar stirrer. The removal efficiency of 13 coagulants on target heavy metals and simulated nuclides

was evaluated under fixed conditions: the initial pH of the waste liquid was adjusted to 8.0, a flocculant dosage of 1 g/L was applied, and the reaction proceeded for 30 minutes, with pH adjustments made using 0.1 M HNO₃ or NaOH solutions. In the flocculation process, the reagent was mixed at 200 rpm for 10 minutes, and then stirred at 50 rpm for 10 minutes to promote the growth of flocs. After settling for 30 minutes, samples were taken at 2 cm below the liquid level. The sample was filtered through a 0.45 μm mixed cellulose ester membrane to precipitate particulate matter. HNO₃ was added to the filtrate to increase its concentration to 2%. Subsequently, the elemental concentration of the acidified filtrate was tested by ICP-OES, and the concentrations of eight target elements in the filtrate were analyzed and determined. This standardized protocol enables objective comparison of flocculant performance under controlled conditions.

In the single-factor experiments, the influences of the following parameters on the efficiency of coagulant #9 were examined: pH at 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10; dosage at 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.25, and 1.5 g/L; and flocculation time at 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 minutes, respectively. Each experimental condition was tested in duplicate, and the results were averaged. The experimental results were substituted into Equation 1 to calculate the removal efficiencies of heavy metals and simulated radionuclides by the flocculant.

$$\eta = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where: η is the removal efficiency (%) of the flocculant for heavy metals and simulated radionuclides; C_0 and C_e represent the initial concentration (mg/L) of heavy metals/simulated radionuclides in the solution and their residual concentration (mg/L) in the filtrate (or effluent) after flocculation treatment, respectively.

Response surface methodology (RSM) experiments

Based on single-factor experiments, the RSM experiment was designed to explore the interaction among different factors and seek the optimal reaction conditions. In this study, RSM was only fitted and optimized within the set design domain, and the conclusions were not extrapolated to the working conditions outside the domain. Compared with traditional orthogonal experiments, RSM can reduce the number of experiments through Box-Behnken design

(BBD) or central composite design (CCD), and combined with analysis of variance (ANOVA), it can reveal the significance of factors and interactions (Czyrski et al. 2020). Although it relies on linear or quadratic polynomial assumptions and has a limited ability to fit high-order nonlinear relationships (Zhang et al. 2020), it remains an excellent method for seeking the best reaction conditions. Therefore, based on the results of the single-factor test, we adopted the central composite design to construct the response surface method model. This model was used to investigate the interactive effects of three key parameters—flocculation time (X_1), dosage (X_2), and pH (X_3)—within the ranges specified in Table 2, on the target response value (radionuclide removal efficiency, η). A total of 17 experimental points were designed. The mathematical relationship between parameter X_i and response value y is fitted by equation (2) second order polynomial model.

$$\eta = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i x_i + \sum_{i=1}^k b_{ii} x_i^2 + \sum_{i < j} \sum_j b_{ij} x_i x_j \quad (2)$$

In the equation, b_0 represents the predicted value of the removal efficiency η at the central point of the experimental design, while b_i , b_{ii} , and b_{ij} denote the coefficients for the linear, quadratic nonlinear, and interaction terms of the parameters X_i , respectively.

Table 2. Parameters and levels for RSM experimental design

Parameter	Variable	Range		
		-1	0	1
X_1	Flocculation time/(minutes)	10	20	30
X_2	Dosage/(g/L)	0.75	1.0	1.25
X_3	pH	7	8	9

Results and discussion

Preliminary screening of flocculants

Under the same operating conditions, when the dosage of flocculant is 1 g/L, the pH is 8.0, and the flocculation time is 30 minutes, the removal efficiencies of the target components by the 13 flocculants are shown in Fig. 1. For elements Pb and Bi, all 13 kinds of flocculants achieved efficient removal, with the removal rate of Pb exceeding 95% and that of Bi reaching over 99%. This is mainly attributed to the fact that at this pH, the two form extremely insoluble hydroxide precipitates. For instance, the solubility product of $\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$ ($K_{sp} = 1.43 \times 10^{-20}$) is extremely small, ensuring the complete progress of the precipitation reaction. At $\text{pH} \approx 8$, Te (present as TeO_4^{2-}) does not precipitate on its own (Chen et al. 2019; WonYong et al. 2022; Yukun et al. 2022). Therefore, its high removal efficiency is achieved through two synergistic mechanisms: first, precipitation by forming insoluble Ag-Te compounds (e.g., Ag_2Te) with Ag^+ in the solution; second, removal via the “enmeshment and sweep coagulation” process during flocculation. Additionally, sulfur-containing ligands (e.g., DTC) can coordinate with Te/Ag-Te, further enhancing the efficiency of

the aforementioned precipitation and flocculation processes, resulting in a significant synergistic effect. Compared with #1 - #7, #8 - #13 showed statistically significant increases in Mn/Co/Ag (see Fig. 1, mean \pm 95%CI), among which #9 performed the best while maintaining nearly neutral effluent (see Table 3). For elements Cs and Sr, all flocculants showed poor removal efficiency for Cs, with the maximum value not exceeding 50%. Except for the removal efficiency of element Sr by flocculants #10 to #12 which is close to 90%, the maximum value of the other flocculants does not exceed 40%. However, it can be seen from the data in Table 3 that flocculants #10 to #12 will cause the pH of the solution to rise, this does not meet our expected effluent pH value (GB 8978-1996). It might be more suitable to remove Cs and Sr by ion exchange process in the future. Therefore, we selected the #9 flocculant with a removal rate of 99% for Pb/Bi/Co/Ag/Mn and 96% for Te, while maintaining a nearly neutral effluent, as the target for process optimization.

Table 3. Changes in wastewater pH after flocculant addition

Coagulant serial number	Initial value	Before flocculation	After flocculation
#1	2.31	8.03	7.6
#2	2.35	8.0	7.32
#3	2.34	8.03	7.65
#4	2.34	8.06	7.41
#5	2.32	8.06	7.43
#6	2.35	8.0	7.35
#7	2.27	8.03	7.62
#8	2.32	8.03	10.08
#9	2.30	8.0	8.03
#10	2.31	8.08	11.78
#11	2.32	8.0	11.72
#12	2.30	8.03	11.79
#13	2.33	8.0	11.77

To clarify the respective contributions of pH-induced precipitation and the intrinsic efficacy of Flocculant #9 to the removal of various nuclides, control experiments were designed. Under identical conditions ($\text{pH} = 8.0$, consistent ionic strength and stirring), the following were measured separately: (1) the removal efficiency (η_{pH}) attributable solely to pH effects in the absence of flocculant; (2) the total removal efficiency (η_{total}) after the addition of Flocculant #9. Additionally, an “Ag-free” parallel experimental system was established to further elucidate the mechanisms. The removal enhancement provided by the flocculant was quantitatively assessed by calculating $\Delta\eta = \Delta\eta = \eta_{\text{total}} - \eta_{\text{pH}}$, with 95% confidence intervals provided. The relevant results are shown in Fig. 2.

As shown in Fig. 2a, for Pb and Bi, whose removal is dominated by hydroxide precipitation, $\Delta\eta$ was only 0–1%, indicating their removal relies primarily on pH conditions. In contrast, for Te, Co, Mn, and Ag, $\Delta\eta$ exceeded 10%, confirming that Flocculant #9 significantly enhances the removal of these elements through complexation and enmeshment/sweep-flocculation. Fig. 2b shows that in the

Figure 1. Comparison of removal efficiencies of 13 commercial flocculants for target pollutants in simulated concentrate (Conditions: Dosage 1 g/L, pH 8.0, Time 30 minutes); **a.** Ag+ flocculant; **b.** Bi+ flocculant; **c.** Te+ flocculant; **d.** Co+ flocculant; **e.** Mn+ flocculant; **f.** Pb+ flocculant; **g.** Sr+ flocculant; **h.** Cs+ flocculant.

Figure 2. a. Removal efficiency before and after the addition of flocculant #9 under pH = 8 conditions; **b.** Removal efficiency of the Ag-free control group before and after the addition of flocculant #9 under pH = 8 conditions.

Ag-free system, the $\Delta\eta$ for Te decreased to 3–5%, and its overall removal efficiency (η) dropped significantly. This further indicates a synergistic effect between silver-tellurium precipitation and the flocculation process.

Single-factor experiments

Effect of pH

As shown in Fig. 3a, for the precipitation-predominant elements (Ag, Bi and Te), within the pH range of 6 to 10, their removal rates remain above 98%, 99% and 96%, respectively. This is mainly attributed to the direct formation of insoluble compounds: Bi^{3+} is transformed into highly insoluble BiOOH , Ag^+ is transformed into Ag_2O ($K_{sp} = 1.2 \times 10^{-8}$), and TeO_4^{2-} to silver tellurium compounds. Within this pH range, the influence of the change in OH^- concentration on the precipitation equilibrium can be ignored, thus maintaining a stable removal effect.

In contrast, the removal behaviors of Pb, Co, and Mn exhibit pronounced pH dependence (Fig. 3b). Under weakly acidic conditions (pH = 6), insufficient OH^- concentration leads to these elements existing predominantly as free ions, resulting in low removal rates. When the pH rises to 7, the removal efficiencies of Pb^{2+} and Co^{2+} reach peak values of 99.52% and 99.09%, respectively, which can be ascribed to the extremely low solubility products of their hydroxides ($\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$ $K_{sp} = 1.43 \times 10^{-20}$; $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ $K_{sp} = 5.9 \times 10^{-15}$). From a thermodynamic perspective, precipitation becomes spontaneous once the ion activity product exceeds the solubility product; the theoretical onset pH for precipitation of each metal can be calculated based on its initial concentration and K_{sp} , providing a reference for interpreting the experimental results. Mn^{2+} achieves its optimum removal (99.34%) at pH = 8, due to the relatively higher K_{sp} of $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_2$ (1.6×10^{-13}), which requires a more alkaline environment to drive the precipitation toward completion.

Figure 3. Removal efficiencies of target pollutants by flocculant #9 at different pH values (Dosage: 1 g/L, Flocculation time: 30 minutes): **a.** Removal efficiencies of Ag, Bi, and Te; **b.** Removal efficiencies of Co, Mn, and Pb; **c.** Removal efficiencies of Sr and Cs.

As for the poorly removable nuclides Sr and Cs (Fig. 3c), their behavior is even more constrained by solubility-product limitations. $\text{Sr}(\text{OH})_2$ has a comparatively large K_{sp} (3.2×10^{-4}); as the pH increases, the solubility of Sr^{2+} gradually decreases, raising its removal efficiency from 12.1% at pH = 6 to 43.5% at pH = 10. However, under the engineering-relevant effluent condition of $\text{pH} \leq 8$, its removal reaches only 18.7%. Because of the exceedingly large K_{sp} of CsOH , Cs^+ remains highly soluble in the aqueous phase, yielding a removal efficiency below 15%. This confirms that pH adjustment alone is ineffective for removing Cs^+ ions.

Effect of dosage

It can be seen from Fig. 4a, b, for saturation-type elements including Ag, Bi, and Pb, removal peaks of 99.89% for Ag, 99.98% for Bi, and 99.88% for Pb were achieved at dosages of 0.5 grams per liter or more, indicating that their removal is primarily governed by pH-induced precipitation rather than flocculant dosage.

For dosage-dependent elements Te, Co, and Mn, the removal efficiency increased linearly with the flocculant dosage. FTIR spectroscopy shown in Fig. 5 revealed a key mechanism: the vibrational peaks of C–S bonds at 855 cm^{-1} and C=S bonds at 1194 cm^{-1} (Lijian et al. 2022) in the flocculant were significantly attenuated in the precipitate containing all elements. In the FTIR spectrum of the flocculant after reaction with Te, the peak intensity of the C=S bond significantly decreased, confirming that Te

atoms in solution formed Te–S coordination bonds with side chains of the flocculant (Majhi et al. 2023). The Te–S bond exhibits strong polarity, which influences the polarity of the C=S bond through an electron induction effect, thereby reducing its infrared absorption intensity. After the reaction of Mn with flocculant, the peak strength of C–S bond also weakened, which is due to the formation of coordination bond between C–S group and Mn, and the participation of lone pair electrons of S atom in bonding, resulting in the decrease of electronegativity and the change of C–S conjugate system, thus causing the change of infrared signal. Co and S form Co–S bond is enhanced. This phenomenon can be attributed to the coordination induced effect of co-s Bond: S atom provides lone pair electrons to the empty orbit of Co, resulting in the reduction of its own electron cloud density, thus enhancing the polarity of C–S bond and enhancing the infrared absorption (Xiang et al. 2016).

The experimental results show that sufficient flocculants are required to provide binding sites in this process. When the dosage was 1.0 g/L, the removal efficiencies of Co and Mn exceeded 99%; When the dosage was increased to 1.5 g/L, the removal efficiency only increases by $\leq 0.5\%$. Therefore, from the perspective of actual process, we judge that the dosage of 1.0 g/L is the most appropriate. For weakly reactive elements Sr and Cs, changes in dosage have minimal impact on the removal efficiency, with Sr showing removal efficiencies between

Figure 4. Removal efficiency and infrared spectrum analysis (pH = 8.0, flocculation time = 30 minutes) of flocculant #9 for each target pollutant under different dosage: **a.** Removal efficiency of Ag, Bi and Te elements; **b.** Removal efficiencies of CO, Mn and Pb elements; **c.** Removal efficiencies of Sr and Cs elements.

Figure 5. Infrared spectra of flocculant, all element sediment, Mn flocculant sediment, Co flocculant sediment, Te flocculant sediment.

21% and 41% and Cs between 6.9% and 19.8%. This indicates the overall performance relies on non-specific physical adsorption, demonstrating the flocculant’s limited effectiveness in removing these two elements.

Effect of flocculation time

Under the conditions of different flocculation time, the removal efficiency of 9# flocculant for different nuclides was studied, the experimental results are shown in Fig. 6. Fig. 6a, b demonstrate that Pb, Bi, Ag, Co, and Mn are fast-equilibrium elements, achieving over 99% removal within 5 minutes. This rapid removal aligns

with the characteristics of precipitation reactions that complete instantaneously, as exemplified by the reaction $Pb^{2+} + 2OH^- \rightarrow Pb(OH)_2 \downarrow$.

However, the removal efficiency of Te gradually increased with prolonged flocculation time (Fig. 6a, e). After 5, 10, and 20 minutes of reaction, the removal rates reached 91.58%, 95.63%, and 96.77%, respectively, and then stabilized. This trend is closely related to the evolution of floc size (Fig. 6e). In the initial stage (5 minutes), flocs consisted mainly of microflocs (1–10 μm) with a large specific surface area but limited capturing capacity. As flocculation progressed (10 minutes), floc size increased rapidly to approximately 10 μm, enabling effective capture of Te–flocculant complexes via bridging. By 20 minutes, the flocs became denser and reached 10–100 μm, at which point their surface chelating sites (e.g., Te–S bonds) and internal entrapment capacity were most favorable, corresponding to the plateau in Te removal. The relationship between Te removal efficiency (Q) and average floc size (d) followed a logistic equation (Equation 3), with a coefficient of determination of 0.998 (Fig. 6d), indicating high reliability of the model. Analysis of the equilibrium inflection point of the fitted curve revealed that a floc size of approximately 24.37 μm during the 10–20 minutes flocculation period served as the critical threshold for efficient Te removal.

$$Q = \frac{L}{1 + e^{-k(d-d_0)}} \quad (3)$$

Where *L*: the maximum value of the curve, *K*: the growth rate of the curve, *d*₀: the midpoint of the curve on the X axis.

Figure 6. Effect of flocculation time on the logistic fitting of removal efficiency, floc particle size and Te removal efficiency (pH = 8.0, dosage = 1 g/L): **a.** removal efficiencies of Ag, Bi and Te elements; **b.** Removal efficiencies of Co, Mn and Pb elements; **c.** Removal efficiencies of Sr and Cs elements; **d.** The logistic regression equation between Te removal efficiency and average particle size of flocs was obtained; **e.** Effect of flocculation time on flocculation particle size.

As shown in Fig. 6c, for the nuclides Sr and Cs, whose removal is dominated by physical adsorption, the removal efficiencies increased slowly with prolonged flocculation time: Sr increased gradually from 15% to 25%, and Cs from 10% to 18%. Combined with the variation of floc size over time presented in Fig. 6e, it can be inferred that as flocculation proceeds, the growing floc size enhances the nonspecific interactions (e.g., van der Waals forces) between the flocs and the ions Sr^{2+} and Cs^+ in solution, thereby improving the physical adsorption capacity (Bruch et al. 2007). This mechanism accounts for the gradually increasing trend in removal efficiency shown in Fig. 6c.

Response surface model

Model construction and significance analysis

In the RSM model, the F-value determines the statistical significance of the regression equation, and the larger the F-value and the smaller the P-value, the higher the significance of the regression equation or factor term. It can be known from the data analysis in Table 4 that the F-value of the model is 12.77, and the P-value is less than 0.05, indicating that the model is significant. According to the P-values of each factor in the model, it can be concluded that the first-order terms X_1 and X_2 are highly significant, while the interaction terms X_1^2 and X_2^2 are significant. At the same time, the model shows insignificant features regarding X_3 , which is consistent with the results of single factor experiments. The coefficient of determination of the equation is $R^2 = 0.9426$, indicating a good fit and the model can accurately reflect the experimental results. The correction determination coefficient $R^2_{\text{adj}} = 0.8688$ indicates that 89.14% of the change in response value comes from the research factors, which means that the model presents significance and can be well used to predict the change in Te removal efficiency.

Response surface analysis and parameter optimization

As shown in Fig. 7, in order to further analyze the influence of experimental parameters, the response surface and contour map of the effect of three research factors

Table 4. ANOVA analysis of the RSM model for Te removal efficiency

term	sum of squares	mean square	degree of freedom	F	P
model	—	—	9	12.77	<0.05
X_1	1.77×10^{-3}	1.77×10^{-3}	1	38.91	<0.0001
X_2	2.145×10^{-3}	2.145×10^{-3}	1	47.15	<0.0001
X_3	5.0×10^{-7}	5.0×10^{-7}	1	0.011	0.9194
$X_1 X_2$	1.0×10^{-6}	1.0×10^{-6}	1	0.022	0.8863
$X_1 X_3$	2.25×10^{-6}	2.25×10^{-6}	1	0.049	0.8304
$X_2 X_3$	2.25×10^{-6}	2.25×10^{-6}	1	0.049	0.8304
X_1^2	5.376×10^{-4}	5.376×10^{-4}	1	11.82	<0.05
X_2^2	5.863×10^{-4}	5.863×10^{-4}	1	12.89	<0.05
X_3^2	6.906×10^{-5}	6.906×10^{-5}	1	1.52	0.2577

on Te removal efficiency are drawn according to the regression equation. The steep response surface and oval contour lines indicate that the interaction between the two experimental factors is significant, otherwise it is not significant. It can be seen from Fig. 7a that the response surface is steep, with dense contour lines and oval shape, indicating that the interaction between flocculant dosage and flocculation time is significant. However, in Fig. 7b, the contour lines are dense but not elliptical, indicating that the interaction between time and pH is not significant. Similarly, in Fig. 7c, contour lines are dense but not elliptical, and the regression coefficient of X_2 and X_3 in the regression equation is -0.75×10^{-4} (less than 0), indicating that there is no interaction between flocculation time and pH. It is found that the change of pH has little effect on the model under the joint action of multiple factors in the experiment. Based on the analysis of the results of single-factor experiments, the specific reason can be attributed to the reaction between Te and Ag in the solution to form insoluble silver-tellurium compounds, which can be precipitated and removed under the complexation effect of the flocculant, and the formation of silver-tellurium compounds is not affected by pH.

Model reliability verification

After obtaining the optimal theoretical parameters of flocculation experiment, the model reliability verification experiment was further carried out, and the results are shown in Fig. 8. It can be seen from the figure that the

Figure 7. Response surface and contour map of Te removal efficiency: **a.** Interaction between time and dosage (pH = 8); **b.** Interaction between time and pH (dosage = 1.0 g/L); **c.** Interaction between dosage and pH (time = 20 minutes).

Figure 8. Removal efficiency of pollutants under RSM optimization verification experiment.

measured Te removal efficiency is 97.1%, which is lower than 97.6% predicted by the model. However, the deviation between the measured value and the predicted value of the removal efficiency is only 0.5%, which can be attributed to the error in the experiment or test link. The removal efficiency of Pb/Bi/Co/Mn/Ag remained > 99% and fluctuated < 0.3%, which proved that the optimized parameters did not interfere with the dominant precipitation mechanism of other elements.

After optimization by response surface methodology, the Te removal efficiency increased from 96.0% to 97.1%, with an increase of 1.1%, and the residual Te concentration decreased from 0.055 mg/L to 0.040 mg/L, with a decrease of 27.55%, providing support for the subsequent ^{210}Po deep purification. The pH of the effluent is 7.8 ± 0.1 , which is strictly in line with the Chinese national standard GB 8978-1996, pH 6-9. The residual element concentration is less than 0.1 mg/L, which is lower than the limit value of the emission standard for heavy metal pollution (GB 31574-2015) in the national standard of China. The residual concentration of Sr/Cs is between 4.0~4.25 mg/L, which requires subsequent process purification. In conclusion, the RSM optimization scheme reduces the concentration of residual Te by 27.55% on the premise of ensuring the removal efficiency of other elements.

Conclusion

This study systematically investigated the optimization of the flocculation-sedimentation process for the removal of heavy metals, fission products, and ^{210}Po simulants from radioactive concentrated solutions in lead-bismuth cooled reactors for consistent term. Flocculant No.9 is a dithiocarbamate. The removal efficiency of Pb, Bi, Co, Mn and Ag is more than 99%, and the removal efficiency of Po simulant is more than 96%. At the same time, it can maintain the pH value of the effluent at about

8.0, showing better performance than the other 12 flocculants. In single-factor experiments, pH was found to be the dominant factor influencing the precipitation of metals such as Pb, Bi, and Ag, with optimal removal efficiencies achieved at pH levels between 7 and 8. The dosage of flocculant affects the removal efficiency of Co, Mn and Te elements. The most cost-effective dosage was 1 g/L, while the peak removal efficiency was attained at 1.5 g/L. With the increase of flocculation time, the particle size of flocs increased, while the chelating adsorption capacity of large particle size flocs for Te was significantly improved. When the flocculation time exceeds 20 minutes and the particle size increases to 10~100 μm , the removal efficiency is significantly improved. The RSM process optimization was conducted with the Te removal efficiency as the objective, and the optimal parameter combination derived from the model was 15.9 minutes, 1.17 g/L, and pH 7.8. The validation experiment confirmed that the Te removal efficiency increased to 97.1%, with a deviation of less than 0.5% from the optimal theoretical removal efficiency after RSM optimization. Meanwhile, the removal efficiencies of other heavy metals remained above 99%. Furthermore, this study suggest that the process conclusions regarding Po are primarily applicable to systems predominantly governed by silver-sulfide precipitation and sulfur-containing ligand complexation. If the actual operating conditions are characterized mainly by Po(IV) hydrolysis or hydroxide precipitation, further scale-up testing combined with actual radioactivity validation is required. Nevertheless, the process proposed herein still offers an efficient and low-cost pretreatment solution for lead-bismuth reactor concentrates. It not only enables deep removal of heavy metals such as Pb and Bi, but also significantly reduces the load of the ^{210}Po simulant, thereby creating favorable conditions for the subsequent deep purification of α -emitting nuclides.

Declaration of competing interest

We declare that we have no financial and personal relationships with other people or organizations that can inappropriately influence our work, there is no professional or other personal interest of any nature or kind in any product, service and/or company that could be construed as influencing the position presented in, or the review of, the manuscript entitled: "Pretreatment of Radioactive Concentrate from Lead-Bismuth Cooled Fast Reactors: Flocculant Screening and Process Optimization".

Acknowledgments

This study was funded by the horizontal project of China Guangdong Nuclear Power Research Institute Co., Ltd. (24zh0506, performance testing for deep purification of heavy metal pollutants in radioactive liquid waste).

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